

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

Storing CO₂ in Demolition Concrete by Forming Calcium Carbonate

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

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Image courtesy: [Neustark AG](#)

About this document:

This document provides a possible approach for the utilization of captured CO₂. Specifically, by production of recycled concrete with captured CO₂ by forming calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) from demolition concrete. This process is integral to reducing carbon emissions in the construction sector with help of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) strategy, encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). Maintaining the 'Neutral' descriptor, these solutions are universally applicable, transcending the limitations of specific geographic sites. 'Solution' signifies a strategic and effective response to these challenges. 'Packages' represents the all-inclusive nature of these solutions, ensuring a holistic approach to the challenges of CO₂ transport and storage. Designed primarily at city administrators and urban planners, this NSP illustrates how the integration of CCUS technology in the processing of concrete demolition can contribute to urban sustainability.

Description:

Demolition Concrete Material (DCM), as the name suggests, is waste construction material that is produced in large quantities during the demolition of concrete buildings and structures. Its use to capture CO₂ has become prevalent in recent years due to its high abundance of calcium cations and high alkaline properties, which could sequester CO₂ by reacting and binding carbon in the form of CaCO₃. This form is very stable, meaning that the carbon from the captured CO₂ in principle will be bound permanently.

Combining CCS technologies with the construction and demolition waste sectors to store CO₂ by forming CaCO₃ has proven to be more sustainable than collecting and using natural limestone for new cement production.

Challenge/Goal:

With more than one billion tons of concrete per year, demolition concrete is the world's single largest waste stream and is considered harmful to the environment (Tiefenthaler, J. et al, 2021). DCM is normally dumped in landfills or illegal dumping sites, leading to increased pollution. This calls for recycling strategies for environmental sustainability, greener production, and economical reuse.

Furthermore, as urbanisation is increasing, with two thirds of the population expected to live in urban areas in three decades, the demand for concrete is estimated to continue to increase by 12-23% by 2050 compared to 2014 (IEA, 2018). As cement is a key element in concrete, the energy-intensive cement sector is also expected to grow, making it the third largest industrial energy consumer globally and one of the highest emitters of all industrial carbon emitters. The goal is to recycle concrete waste, enable permanent carbon dioxide storage in urban domain and reduce the carbon footprint of new infrastructure. This, in turn, contributes to the transition to a more sustainable construction industry by providing a solution that addresses both carbon emissions and waste management.

Solution:

A promising solution is the capture of CO₂ from biogenic sources by binding it in the form of very stable CaCO₃ in recycled concrete. By capturing emitted CO₂ from biogas plants and mineralizing it as limestone bound to the demolition concrete granules' surface, a permanent carbon storage is obtained, whilst simultaneously achieving negative emissions, as the source of the emitted carbon is of a biogenic nature. Then processed granules could be further used for infrastructure projects or for production of fresh recycled concrete (Neustark, n.d.).

Implementation Process:

The current recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) is used to sequester CO₂. For doing this, RCA is put into a tight reactor. Then CO₂ is fed into the reactor to generate a 100 % CO₂ atmosphere at ambient pressure and temperature. This leads to the reaction of cement and CO₂. The calcium carbonate forms microscopic structures at the surface of the grains. It cannot be separated. The RCA is then used as usual for mixing fresh concrete, as filler material in road construction or landfill.

Corresponding timeline based on interviews conducted with the relevant stakeholders:

Phase	Duration	Description
Initial Research	0-3 Months	Preliminary research and concept development.
Feasibility Study	3-6 Months	Technical, environmental, and economic assessment.
Stakeholder Engagement	4-9 Months	Engage with stakeholders and secure partnerships.
Design and Engineering	6-12 Months	Detailed facility and process design.

Compliance and Permits	9-15 Months	Regulatory compliance and permit acquisition.
Pilot Testing	12-18 Months	Validate technology and processes.
Construction Preparation	15-21 Months	Equipment procurement and construction preparation.
Construction and Setup	18-30 Months	Facility construction and equipment installation.
Testing and Commissioning	24-36 Months	Operational testing and system commissioning.
Full-Scale Operation	30+ Months	Start full-scale operation and monitoring.

Regulations and laws:

Production of cement that stores captured CO₂ by forming CaCO₃ from demolition concrete operates within a complex regulatory environment, particularly in Europe. Although a unified regulatory framework specific to this process is not yet established, the momentum of the European Green Deal significantly impacts the sector. This strategy underscores the importance of CCS and CCU technologies in achieving the net zero goals. Key points include:

1. **CCS SET-Plan 2030:** This plan outlines the advancement and integration of CCS technologies within the EU, setting ambitious goals to enhance these technologies for a broader and more effective implementation.
2. **CCS EU Directive:** This directive ensures the safe implementation of CCS technologies in a manner that protects both the environment and human health.
3. **GHG Performance Based Certification:** The EU is developing certification systems that focus on the GHG performance of low-carbon materials and carbon removal techniques. Such certifications could play a crucial role in validating the environmental impact of the CaCO₃ production process.
4. **Building Permits and Local Regulations:** Production facilities must obtain building permits from relevant authorities, adhering to local and national environmental standards.

Citizen Engagement and City-Company Collaboration:

1. **Educational Initiatives:** Launch educational programmes to inform citizens about the environmental benefits of capturing CO₂ in recycled concrete, highlighting its role in reducing CO₂ emissions and promoting circular economy practices.
2. **Local Government Partnerships:** Collaborate with city authorities to integrate this recycling process into urban waste management and sustainability roadmaps, flag benefits of recycled concrete for public procurement. This includes seeking regulatory approval support and exploring potential funding opportunities.
3. **Showcasing Benefits:** Highlight direct benefits to the local community, such as reduced landfill use, job creation in the recycling and construction sectors, and the long-term environmental benefits of sustainable construction practices.

4. **Industry-Local Collaborations:** Foster partnerships between companies involved in recycled concrete production and local public service organisations, e.g. potentially using the CO₂ captured from regional WtE plants, creating a closed-loop system.
5. **Transparency in operations:** Maintain transparency in the production process, including environmental impact, technological advancements, and safety measures, to build trust and support among the local population.
6. **Incorporating EU Guidelines:** align the project with EU guidelines and policies on carbon capture and use, waste management, and urban sustainability, ensuring compliance with broader environmental goals.

Lessons learned/ Impact:

- The described process enables permanent storage of CO₂. That means that even if the recycled concrete in which CO₂ is ejected is demolished, the stored carbon would not be released into the air. CaCO₃ is one of the most permanent ways to sequester carbon. Only temperatures above 600 degrees Celsius or very strong acids can trigger its release in the atmosphere.
- Storage capacity: currently around 10 kg of CO₂ per ton of demolition concrete. Depending on the specifics of the material, this figure could increase to 25 kg of CO₂ per ton.
- The technology is scalable due to inclusion of different actors in the value chain: by broadly deploying the technology at various sites throughout Europe, the possibility of operational cost reduction increases. Hence, the price of carbon removal and storage decreases.
- Removal efficiency: according to life cycle analysis (LCA), this CCS technology reaches a carbon removal efficiency of 93% over the whole lifespan (i.e., 7% of the CO₂ is re-emitted as grey emission).

Advice for replication:

1. **CO₂ source collaboration:** Establish agreements with CO₂ emitting facilities employing carbon capture technologies, such as biogas or cement plants, to maintain a steady supply of CO₂.
2. **Financial planning:** Develop financial models specific to concrete demolition processing and recycled concrete production, considering both costs and potential revenue streams.
3. **Regulatory Compliance:** Ensure adherence to environmental standards and seek certifications that highlight the sustainability of the recycled concrete produced.
4. **Community engagement:** Educate local stakeholders about the environmental benefits of this recycling process to obtain support.
5. **Market opportunities:** Identify markets for the produced recycled concrete, such as construction or manufacturing, public procurement contracts, to ensure economic viability.

6. **Best-Practices Documentation:** Document and share the process and learnings for global replication and adoption.

SWOT analysis:

Strengths	Weaknesses
Environmental impact: Reduced CO ₂ emissions due to the implementation of technology can contribute to environmental sustainability and compliance with emissions regulations.	Limited availability of high-quality demolition concrete: The availability of high-quality demolition concrete may be limited in some areas due to the lack of pre-selection prior demolition. Waste stream separation based on concrete properties is also required to improve the quality.
Reduces waste: This technology can help reduce the amount of demolition concrete sent to landfills.	
Produces a valuable product: demand for cement is predicted only to grow in the next decades.	
Threats	Opportunities
Insufficient availability of CO ₂ relative to the availability of demolition concrete.	Replication: The successful implementation of this solution can be replicated in other industrial plants, expanding the adoption of energy-efficient carbon capture.
	Environmental compliance: Meeting emissions regulations and reducing the carbon footprint can enhance the plant's compliance and reputation.
	Public-private partnerships: There are opportunities for collaboration with local governments, private investors, and technology providers to secure funding and support.
	Growing demand for cement: The demand is growing driven by increasing industrialization and urbanisation

The SWOT analysis of the production of cement that stores captured CO₂ by forming CaCO₃ from demolition concrete highlights a wide spectrum of key points. Importantly, it's worth noting that for city representatives involved in procurement processes, there are no relevant threats or weaknesses, as the production and demand aspects fall within the responsibility sphere of producers. Cities primarily benefit from the environmental and sustainability-related aspects of utilizing this type of cement in their construction projects. Additionally, effective educational outreach with citizens can lead to the city benefiting of public support. Furthermore, employing this type of cement in infrastructure projects aligns with the overarching objective of decarbonizing urban areas and economies, further supporting the city's efforts in this regard.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

<u>Title</u>	<u>Autor</u>	<u>Year</u>	<u>Link</u>
Application of demolished concrete material (DCM) in civil engineering structures - Review.	Mohammed Ali et al.	2018	researchgate.net
How our solution works - neustark	neustark	-	neustark
A new concept of calcium carbonate concrete using demolished concrete and CO ₂ .	Ippei Maruyama et al.	2021	jst.go.jp
The Chemistry Behind Concrete: A Comprehensive Look at Chemical Compounds and Reactions	Zaid Faridi	2021	Concrete Decor
Mitigating Carbon Dioxide Emissions in Cement through Carbon Capture and Storage	Nicholas Cramer	-	calpoly.edu
Technology roadmap: Low-Carbon Transition in the Cement Industry	International Energy Agency (IEA)	2020	windows.net
EU Policy and Support for Developing CCS	Maria Velkova, European Commission	2020	bcforum.net
CCS Roadmap to 2030	Carbon Capture & Storage Association	2022	CCS-setplan.eu
Recycling of calcined carbonated cement pastes as cementitious materials: Proposed CCS technology for calcium looping	Y.K.Kong, S. Ruan, Kiyofumi Kurumisawa	2022	ScienceDirect

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<https://www.neustark.com/en/how-our-solution-works> den 17 January 2024
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